

20th International Forum on Knowledge Asset Dynamics

Book of Papers

collection of papers presented at
IFKAD 2025

**Knowledge Futures: AI, Technology,
and the New Business Paradigm**

2-4 July 2025
University of Naples Federico II
Naples, Italy

20th International Forum on Knowledge Asset Dynamics

BOOK OF PAPERS

collection of papers presented at

IFKAD 2025

Knowledge Futures: AI, Technology, and the New Business Paradigm

2-4 July 2025

University of Naples Federico II

Naples, Italy

ISBN 978-88-96687-18-5

INDEX

- 14 *Claudia Cozzio, Francisco Santos Arteaga, Oswin Maurer*
AI Perceptions Across Organizational Levels: Barriers and Drivers of Adoption in the Hotel Industry
- 23 *Tommaso Di Fonzo*
Artificial Intelligence Adoption in South Tyrolean Hospitality: A Qualitative Analysis
- 31 *Haschka Rouven Edgar*
A Truncated Poisson Model to Approximate the Firm-Level Innovation Generation Process
- 38 *Luca Tuporini, Vittorio D'Amato, Joao Vieira da Cunha, Elena Tosca*
The Interdependent Relationship of MI and Culture: Insights from a Systematic Literature Network Analysis
- 47 *Giuseppe Zangari, Antonio Lorena, Ludovica Zoccali, Rocco Reina*
Organizational Practices for Agile Work: A Systematic Review on Smart Working Strategies
- 55 *Valerio Brescia, Giuseppe Nicolò*
Knowledge Management and Diversity Management in HEIs: An Italian Overview
- 64 *Filomena Buonocore, Davide de Gennaro, Viviana Colombi Evangelista, Ludovica Del Barone, Floriana Pollio*
Rethinking Fairness in Work-Life Policies: A Conceptual Framework Beyond Parenthood
- 72 *Giuseppe Maria Bifulco, Fabrizio Maria Bertusi, Leonzio Capparelli*
ESG and AI: The Role of a New Player in the Sustainability's Game. Explorative Analysis of the Potential Impact of Artificial Intelligence in Business Sustainable Performance
- 80 *Beatrice Sveva Stasi, Fabrizia Sarto, Sara Saggese*
Women Directors, Sustainability Knowledge and Greenwashing: A Study on Italian Companies
- 88 *Francesca Dal Mas, Anna Prenestini, Lorenzo Cobiانchi*
Can Diversity Be an Opportunity to Enhance Ethics? Findings from a Multinational Survey in the Context of Trauma and Emergency Surgery
- 96 *Szu-Chieh Chen, Wei-Ling Yang, Yafang Tsai, Shih-Wang Wu*
Assessing Carbon Emissions and Energy Use Behaviours among Medical Undergraduate Students in Taiwan
- 104 *Vincenzo Pontrelli, Angela Rella, Lara Oliva, Arcangelo Marrone*
Assessing Firm-Level Drivers of High-Quality DE&I Disclosure in Corporate Sustainability Reports: A Stakeholder-Centric Perspective
- 112 *Armando Calabrese, Sofia Carrino, Roberta Costa, Eugenio Roberti, Luigi Tiburzi*
Skill Mismatch: Exploring the Impact of Generative AI in Detecting Biases and Discrimination in Job Advertisements
- 120 *Daria Podmetina, Merle Küttim, Wolfgang Gerstlberger*
The Role of University-Industry-Government Cooperation in Estonia for Sustainable Innovation
- 128 *Francesca Valentina Giglio Moro, Carlo Drago*
Addressing Gender Bias in AI Business Implementation: A Latent Dirichlet Allocation-Based Analysis
- 135 *Marco Tutino, Simona Arduini, Chiara Di Mario*
Artificial Intelligence and Gender Roles: A Structured Literature Review (SLR)
- 144 *Simona Arduini, Tommaso Beck, Tommaso Mattei*
Gender Bias: How Artificial Intelligence Can Reinforce or Reduce Stereotypes
- 152 *Pedro Seva-Larrosa, Giuseppe Modaffari, Francisco García-Lillo*
Digital Technologies in the Knowledge Era: Opportunity or Challenge for Female Entrepreneurship?
- 160 *Maria Teresa Bianchi, Raffaele de Socio, Sabrina Ricco*
AI Impact on the Corporate Gender Gap
- 168 *Alessandro Galli*
Digital Transformation and Gender Equality in Public Administration: An Analysis of NRRP Policies and Implementation
- 177 *Paola Paoloni, Veronica Procacci, Silvia Ievolella*
Industrial Districts and Women-Led SMEs: A Literature Analysis
- 187 *Irene Fulco, Francesca Loia, Barbara Aquilani, Marcello Martinez*
Investigating Digital Transformation and Business Model Innovation in Made in Italy Sectors

INDEX

- 196 *Veronica Marozzo, Fabrizio Cesaroni, Tindara Abbate*
Artificial Intelligence in Social Media Advertising: To Say or Not To Say?
- 202 *Chiara Avarello, Antonia Cava, Veronica Marozzo, Francesco Micali, Andrea Nucita, Stefano Russo*
Exploring AI Integration in Sicilian SMEs: An Investigation on Awareness and Perspectives
- 208 *Tindara Abbate, Fabrizio Cesaroni, Antonio Crupi, Mattia Fasano, Elvira Tiziana La Rocca, Raffaele Staglianò*
Digital Finance for SMEs and Startups: Literature Review and Research Proposals
- 216 *Joachim Dehais*
Enterprise Architecture Model for Knowledge Assets
- 224 *Leonardo Santoro, Gabriele Santoro*
Looking for Co-Founders: Exploring the Co-Founders Selection Process in Venture Studios
- 232 *Maria Cristina Pietronudo, Mario Sorrentino, Elena Candelo*
Bridging Innovation and Market: An Exploratory Analysis of AI Startup Value Propositions
- 238 *Luca Simone Macca, Gabriele Santoro*
Exploring Configurations of Growth Hacking Success Factors in SMEs: An FSQCA Approach
- 247 *Cannavale Chiara, Claudio Lorenza, Diana Koroleva*
Entrepreneurs' Perceptions of AI: Level of Adoption, Competences, and Learning Ecosystem
- 253 *Cristina Caterina Amitrano, Gabriella Esposito, Mark Anthony Camilleri, Stefano Bresciani*
Empowering Disadvantage Entrepreneurship: The Role of New Technologies for People With Disabilities
- 259 *Carmine Passavanti, Tatiana Lopez, Pierluigi Rippa, David Urbano*
Institutional Perspectives on Entrepreneurial Education Ecosystems: Fostering Digital Student Startups
- 267 *Francesca Ventimiglia, Edoardo D'Andrassi, Renato Bellesini, Yael Piperno*
Generative AI in Startups: Challenges, Opportunities, and Theoretical Perspectives on Adoption and Implementation
- 274 *Mario Tani, Gianpaolo Basile*
AI and Entrepreneurship: A Bibliometric Exploration in the Post-ChatGPT Era
- 284 *Valerio Brescia, Ginevra Degregori, Alberto Cavazza*
Artificial Intelligence and Knowledge Management in Healthcare: A Pathway to SDGs Achievement
- 298 *Claudio D'Alonzo*
The Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Business Ethics
- 304 *Antonio Cimino, Vincenzo Corvello, Francesco Longo, Vittorio Solina*
Human-Centered Factors in Generative Artificial Intelligence Adoption: Implications for Employee Well-Being
- 312 *Navigating the Digital Challenge: A Bibliometric Analysis of Talent Management in the Public Sector*
- 322 *Déborá Cristina De Andrade Vicente, Ivan Luciano Danesi, Marta Bertolaso, Chiara Bellini, Lucia Marchegiani*
Corporate Governance, Human-Centric Approaches, and AI Adoption: Does Organizational Size Matter?
- 331 *Barbara Iannone, Marialuigia Di Giampietro*
Sustainability and Well-Being in Industry 5.0: A Systematic Literature Review
- 342 *Manuela Paolini, Fausto Di Vincenzo, Domenico Raucci, Federica Morandi*
Fostering Knowledge Management to Enhance Innovative Work Behaviour in Public Healthcare Organizations
- 350 *Maria Cristina Manocchio, Yasir Faheem, Antonia Puccio, Francesca Di Virgilio*
SMEs AI Investments and Resilience: a Knowledge Risk Perspective
- 358 *Buyan-Arvijikh Boldbaatar, Augusto Colongo, Marco Greco, Paolo Landoni*
Human Resource Management in Early-Stage Startups: A Qualitative Multiple-Case Study
- 369 *Testa Federica, Petrolo Damiano, Giampaola Valerio*
Inclusive Language in Academia: Evaluating Human and AI-Generated Communications to Students
- 377 *Elona Çera, Blerina Dhrami, Comfort Adebisi Asamoah*
Unlocking Innovation in SMEs Through Transformational Leadership and Commitment-based HRM Practices

INDEX

- 385 *Alessandro Massaro, Giuseppe Loseto, Francesco Santarsiero, Giovanni Schiuma, Angelo Rosa, Parisa Sabbagh, Olivia McDermott*
Project “Telediabetolab”: Knowledge Gain and AI Data Process Applied in Telediabetology
- 391 *Edoardo D’Andrassi, Maria Vergallito, Greta Bogo, Davide Ceresa*
A Bibliometric Analysis of Artificial Intelligence and Strategic Knowledge Management: Trends, Gaps and Managerial Implications
- 399 *Heidi Salokangas, Nina Helander, Juha Koivistoinen, Kaisa Sorsa, Heli Aramo-Immonen*
Tacit Knowledge Externalisation in the Context of Sustainability to Strengthen Company Resilience
- 405 *Vadim Smirnov, Bojan Grebić, Snežana Lakićević, Jovana Savković*
Knowledge Management in the Artificial Intelligence Era: Do We Still Need People to Transfer Organizational Knowledge?
- 413 *Nina Helander, Krishna Venkitachalam, Hannele Väyrynen*
Public-Private Co-Creation of Knowledge-Based Open Innovations: Challenges and Opportunities
- 420 *Francesco Pucci, Giuseppe Roberto Marseglia, Alberto Irace, Federico Chmet*
AI-Enhanced Data Platforms: Transforming Knowledge Management in Waste Management Organizations
- 427 *Gianluca Aquilone, Vincenzo Varriale, Antonello Cammarano, Francesca Michelino, Mauro Caputo*
The Role of AI and Emerging Technologies in Transforming Knowledge Management
- 437 *Maayan Nakash, Ettore Bolisani*
Do Organizations Struggle to Implement AI in Knowledge Management Systems? Initial Empirical Insights
- 444 *Maria Rosaria Sessa, Valentina Cicalese, Roberto De Luca, Claudio Del Regno, Ornella Malandrino*
How Artificial Intelligence Technologies Support the Management of Knowledge, Skills and Attitudes of Employees: A Systematic Literature Review
- 454 *Mirko Perano, Claudio Del Regno, Marco Pellicano, Agim Mamuti*
Rethinking Knowledge Management: AI’s Revolutionary Impact on Strategic Management and Corporate Intelligence
- 462 *Shuyun Zhao, Krishna Venkitachalam*
Role of Artificial Intelligence in Organizational Knowledge Creation in PSFs: A Semi-Systematic Review
- 470 *Maria Elena Latino, Maria Chiara De Lorenzi, Maria Laura Giangrande*
AI-driven Value Creation in Innovation Ecosystem, insights from Stakeholder Theory
- 479 *Gerardo Luisi*
Empowering Recognition of Clean-Tech Startup Potential to Address the Climate Change Problem: An Agent-Based Simulation
- 485 *Roberto Cerchione, Patrizia Ghisellini, Renato Passaro, Ivana Quinto, Viviana Sicardi*
The Role of Circular Startups in Circular Innovative Ecosystems: an Italian Multiple Case Study
- 493 *Marta Menegoli, Damiano Calò, Angelo Corallo*
Can Artificial Intelligence Support Companies in Implementing Sustainable Innovation Strategies? Evidence from Agri-Food Companies
- 504 *Adriana Baselice, Alessandra De Chiara, Sofia Mauro*
Exploring the Preliminary Conditions for Blockchain Credibility in the Agri-food Industry
- 512 *Sergio Conterjnic, Cristina Simone, Antonio Laudando*
Analyzing the Excellence in the Agrifood “Made in Italy”: The Italian High-Quality Wine Value Chain and the Role of New Technologies
- 521 *Gerarda Fattoruso, Antonio Violi, Massimo Squillante*
Multi-Criteria Decision-Making to Evaluate Sustainability and Performance in the Agri-Food Supply Chain
- 529 *The Role of Intelligent Packaging in Reducing Food Waste: A Consumer Behaviour Analysis*
- 538 *Walter Vesperi, Maria Carlotta Rizzuto, Anna Maria Melina*
Organizing the Agri-Food Supply Chain to Reduce Food Waste: An Exploratory Study
- 545 *Francesco Santoro, Ada Biafore, David Toscano*
The Kilowatt Project: An Overview about Aims, Tools, and Key Activities

INDEX

- 552 *Gabriela Citlalli López Torres, Octavio Hernandez Castorena, Alba Rocio Carvajal Sandoval*
SME Performance through Modern Technology and Sustainable Business Strategies
- 559 *José Octavio Contreras Sánchez, Vianney Viridiana Contreras Sánchez, Francisco Javier Álvarez-Torres*
Proposal for an Inclusive and Sustainable Telemedicine Ecosystem in Mexico
- 565 *Ana Lidia Quintero Ramírez, Francisco Javier Álvarez-Torres, Giovanni Schiuma, Gabriela Citlalli López-Torres, María D. De-Juan-Vigaray, Clara María Freire Margaça*
The Role of Human Expertise in Digital Transformation and Innovation of SMEs
- 572 *Elizabeth Real Catarina Morais*
Cultural Intelligence and Sustainable Entrepreneurship Strategies to Success in a Global Context
- 582 *Oscar Alejandro Espinoza Mercado, Juan Antonio Vargas Barraza*
Analyzing Innovative Marketing Strategies within SME's in the Restaurant Industry: A Knowledge-Based Approach
- 590 *Peter Lindgren, Jane Flarup, Purnima Lala Mehta, Anmol Bhatia*
How Does AI impact Human Capital and Capability (HCC) in MBMI Processes?
- 599 *Jovana Popovic, Milica Vukotic*
Exploring Technology Diffusion for Enhanced Energy Efficiency: An Empirical Approach
- 606 *Maria Elena Latino, Marta Menegoli, Roberta Pellegrino, Antonio Piepoli, Pierpaolo Pontrandolfo*
What Regenerative Approaches Drive Resilience? A Knowledge Frame for Social-Ecological Systems
- 617 *Sara Matino, Gabriele Luigi Gravina, Luca Mainetti, Roberto Vergallo*
GenAI-aided Sustainable Digital Transformation: A Novel Framework and Early Results
- 626 *Francesca Lerario, Achille Claudio Garavelli, Valentina De Carolis, Daniela Fico, Daniela Rizzo, Carola Esposito Corcione*
Designing 3D-Printed Biocomposites for Quarry Renaturalization: Evaluating a Regenerative Business Model
- 635 *Diana Smite*
Collaborative Hackathons: Enabling Corporate Sustainability Transitions. The Case of Riga Technical University Coopetition
- 645 *Giovanna Ferraro, Antonio Iovanella, Alessandro Ramponi*
An Analysis of Fintech Patents in the Lights of Green Technologies
- 655 *Profiroiu Constantin Marius, Profiroiu Alina Georgiana, Constantin Daniela-Lumiņa, Cibu Bianca Raluca, Delcea Camelia*
Understanding Socio-Economic Perceptions Complexity in Romania and Moldova: Implications for the Business Environment
- 664 *Vincenzo Maione, Cristina Ponsiglione, Simonetta Primario, Manfred Paier, Theresa Buerscher*
Mapping Twin Transitions in Regional Innovation Systems: A Configurational Approach
- 674 *Roberta De Cristofaro, Vincenzo Del Duca, Cristina Ponsiglione, Simonetta Primario, Serena Strazzullo*
Addressing the Complexity of the Green Hydrogen Value-Chain: An Agent-Based Modelling Approach
- 682 *Stephan Leitner*
Organisational Resilience and Decision-Making Modes: An Agent-Based Analysis
- 689 *Carmine Passavanti, Simonetta Primario, Pierluigi Rippa*
Institutional Conditions in Entrepreneurial Education Ecosystems: Effects on Entrepreneurial Knowledge and Culture
- 697 *Adrian Domenteanu, Ioana Ioanăș, Andra Sandu, Delcea Camelia, Liviu-Adrian Cotfas*
Using Artificial Intelligence for Employee Retention Analysis in Complex Environments
- 706 *Linda Ponta, Raffaella Manzini, Silvano Cincotti*
Technology Leaders and Followers: An Agent-Based Approach
- 713 *Raimonda Agne Medeisiene*
How to Support New Knowledge and Business Development Using Applied Theatre: A Case Study
- 720 *Linda Ponta, Andrea Urbinati, Raffaella Manzini*
Circular Economy Yes or No? This is the Dilemma. An Agent-Based Approach

INDEX

- 726 *Martina Percuoco, Anna Prisco, Irene Ricciardi, Vincenzo Dell'Anno*
Artificial Intelligence for a Sustainable Future: Unraveling its Impact on Circular Economy
- 734 *Mariarosalba Angrisani, Marcello Risitano, Marco Ferretti*
Skilling and Upskilling within Port Authority Management: A Strategic Approach to Industry 5.0 Requirements
- 740 *Kristaps Banga, Elina Gaile - Sarkane*
The Bridge Maker's Role in Industry 5.0 Ecosystems: Driving Collaboration and Innovation for Sustainable Outcomes
- 747 *Isabella Bonacci, Maria Menshikova, Danila Scarozza*
Evolution of HRM: Longitudinal Analysis of HR Specialists' Skills in Italy
- 756 *Rasma Pipiķe, Elīna Gaile- Sarkane*
The Role of Top Management Teams' Educational Diversity in Enterprise Performance through the Lens of Upper Echelons Theory
- 765 *Emma Tambou Marianna, Jahan Ara Peerally*
Collaborative Skills and the Evolving Techno-Social Employee Profiles for Manufacturing Firms under the Digitalization Era
- 773 *Maria Eugenia Sánchez Vidal, David Cegarra Leiva*
Shifting Operational HRM to AI: Opportunities, Challenges and Strategic Pathways
- 781 *Minh Hieu Nguyen*
Enhancing Value Creation with Metro Systems: Future Directions Through AI and Intellectual Capital
- 788 *Antonino Interdonato*
Artificial Intelligence as a Lever for Intellectual Capital in Public Administration
- 796 *Esri Nyituriki*
Artificial Intelligence and Microfinance: Enhancing Social Inclusion and Value Creation for Immigrant Communities
- 804 *Vincenzo Belfiore, Alberto Caratozzolo, Valeria Naciti, Daniela Rupo*
AI-driven Transformation in the Pharmaceutical Industry: Value Creation through Strategic Collaboration
- 813 *Antonietta Cosentino, Carla Morrone, Salvatore Principale, Alessandro Sura*
Remote Working and Public Administration: Implications for Relationships with External Users
- 820 *Annaluce Mandiello, Federica Zeuli, Francesco Schiavone*
Digital Therapeutics and Music: A Transdisciplinary Approach in Healthcare
- 827 *Damiano Cortese, Cecilia Casalegno*
What if...? Narratives, Stakeholders and Alternate Endings in Value Creation
- 833 *Antonio Iazzi, Simona Lamusta, Paola Scorrano, Monica Fait*
Bibliometric Exploration of Impression Management and Emerging Technologies in Business Communication
- 843 *Paola Pisano, Rossella Lombardo, Rebecca Bognetti, Rebecca Piolatto, Samuele Rea, Francesco Ricasoli, Elisa Lurago, Maria Antonia Ventriglia, Federico Giorgi*
AI Adoption by Italian Startups: A Measurement Framework
- 852 *Maria Caligaris, Melissa Macaluso, Rossella Lombardo, Paola Pisano*
Interdisciplinary Framework for AI-Powered Restoration Storytelling
- 860 *Caterina Pozzan, Anna Tiso, Azemeraw Tadesse Mengistu, Chiara Verbano*
Challenges of Implementing Healthcare Lean Management in Territorial Healthcare: Insights from an Unsuccessful Case
- 868 *Eleonora Gheduzzi, Mattia Vincenzo Olive, Luca Gastaldi, Cristina Masella*
How Artificial Intelligence Reshapes the Role of Professionals: Preliminary Evidence From a Qualitative Study
- 877 *Chiara Pamich, Anna Tiso, Chiara Verbano*
Enhancing Quality Management in Paediatric Palliative Care Pathways: A Systematic Literature Review
- 884 *Emanuela Foglia, Federica Asperti, Sara Pozzi, Federico Filippo Orsini, Giulia Lanzi*
Transforming Healthcare with AI: Assessing Barriers and Impacts, in a Systematic Review

INDEX

- 893 *Armando Calabrese, Roberta Costa, Francesca Di Pillo, Valerio Schiaroli, Simona Sedda, Luigi Tiburzi*
Integrating the Business Model Concept for the Development of Physicians' Dual Practice in Public Healthcare Delivery Systems
- 902 *Luigi Jesus Basile*
From Innovation to Integration: A Bibliometric-Systematic Review of Digital Therapeutics and Their Impact on Healthcare
- 909 *Salvatore Ammirato, Alessandro Russo, Laura Cutri, Roberto Linzalone*
Driving the Potential Application of AI in Time-Sensitive Clinical Workflows: A Case Study on Stroke Care
- 921 *Lorella Cannavacciuolo, Paolo Mancuso, Alessandro Scarpa*
Exploring the Intricate Relationship between Artificial Intelligence and Healthcare Organizations
- 929 *Fabiola Colmenero Fonseca, Amparo Borrell, Lauren Yolanda Gómez Zamorano, Rut Benavente*
Technology and Heritage: Artificial Intelligence Applied to the Diagnosis and Conservation of Ceramic Materials
- 935 *Ilaria Mariani, Marzia Mortati, Francesca Rizzo*
Designing and Scaling GovTech Solutions Through Stakeholder Engagement. The Case Study of WiseTown's Digital Twin
- 945 *Sabrina Picone*
Artificial Intelligence and the Future of Copyright Law
- 952 *Cristina Simone, Maria Antonietta De Cesare*
Platform Capitalism and the State: Between a New Balance of Power and Geopolitical Competition
- 961 *Marco Chironi, Benedetta Coluccia*
Cybersecurity in the Legal Context: State of Art and Next Challenges
- 969 *Dóra Horváth, Noémi Szilvia Lőrincz*
The Impact of AI on Patient Interactions in Healthcare: Towards Dehumanisation or Rehumanisation?
- 977 *Alba Maria Gallo, Ubaldo Comite, Eveny Ciurleo*
Human-Machine Interaction and Robotics in Healthcare: A Research Programme as a Starting Point
- 982 *Guendalina Capece, Tindaro Cicero, Daniela D'Auria, Flavia Di Costa*
Specific Learning Disabilities (SLD) and Artificial Intelligence (AI): A Bibliometric Analysis
- 989 *Ivone Junges, Clarissa Carneiro Mussi, Eduardo Anibal Blanco*
Artificial Intelligence as a Tool for Building Innovative Organizational Strategies in Market Consolidation
- 997 *Gabriella Esposito, Stefano Bresciani, Ciro Troise, Simona Alfiero*
Governance for Transition: Regulatory Incentives and Stakeholder Engagement in the New European Bauhaus
- 1003 *Ciro Troise, Stefania Testa, Gabriella Esposito, Guido Giovando*
Crowdfunding Failures: An Opportunity for Stakeholder Collaboration?
- 1008 *Barbara Fasoli Braccini, Federico Gaeta*
How the Three-Dimensional Porter Model Redefines Value Creation: Framework, Analysis and Application
- 1017 *Nibedita Saha, Nabanita Saha, Tomas Sáha, Sharad Srivastava, Petr Sáha*
New Collaborative Ecosystems: Do they Create Stirring Dynamics on Footwear Industries Value Chain and Business Network to Integrate Societal Challenges?
- 1024 *Sara Ianniello, Livio Cricelli, Serena Strazzullo*
The Role of Technology in Advancing Sustainability: Insights from the Textile Industry
- 1034 *Nicolò Gianmauro Totaro, Mariasimona Miglietta, Angelo Corallo, Massimiliano Gervasi*
Big Data Technology Maturity Model: Exploring User Perceptions
- 1041 *Andrea Gargiulo, Daniele Leone, Marco Ferretti*
A Sustainable Future for Media-Franchising's Role in the Entertainment Industry
- 1046 *Vito Del Vecchio, Martina De Giovanni, Ayotobi Oromiye Holo, Mariangela Lazoi*
Key Factors for Leveraging and Capitalizing Digital Transformation Initiatives in Industrial Landscape
- 1056 *Sajjad Ahmed, Miguel Mira da Silva, Alberto Rodrigues da Silva, Mariangela Lazoi*
A Comparative Analysis of Low-Code/No-Code Frameworks

INDEX

- 1066 *Alessia Anna Catalano, Christian Catalano, Andrea Chezzi, Vito Del Vecchio*
Thriving Through Digital Change: Building Resilient, Adaptive and Sustainable Organizations
- 1076 *Noémi Szilvia Lőrincz*
Driving or Being Driven: AI Integration in Automotive Supplier Operations and Strategy
- 1085 *Vito del Vecchio, Mariangela Lazoi, Fabio Paracchini, Giorgia Specchia*
Measuring Innovation in Large ICT Firms: A Bibliometric Analysis
- 1095 *Kaisa Sorsa, Heidi Salokangas, Heli Aramo-Immonen*
Sustainability Maturity Models in the Context of Quality Management
- 1101 *Antonio Lorena, Anna M. Correale, Alessia Talarico, Rocco Reina*
The Impact of Artificial Intelligence on the Development of Soft Skills: Opportunities and Challenges for Organizations
- 1109 *Dario Barberini, Maria Giovina Pasca, Gabriella Arcese*
Blockchain for the Circular Economy: Implications and Future Directions
- 1116 *Federica Marroni*
Exploring Artificial Intelligence in the Circular Blue Economy
- 1125 *Vitiana L'Abate, Nicola Raimo, Felice Petruzzella, Antonio Salvi, Filippo Vitolla*
National Culture and Circular Economy Disclosure through Sustainability Reports
- 1133 *Candida Bussoli, Ilenia Fraccalvieri*
Circular Economy Disclosure and Bank Market Value: Evidence from Europe
- 1142 *Giovanna Afeltra, Maria Menshikova*
The Intersection between Circular Economy and Knowledge Management: The Role of Digital Technologies
- 1152 *Patrizia Pastore, Antonio Ricciardi, Gianmarco Salzillo, Silvia Tommaso*
Interfirm Aggregations for Circular Economy Transition in Italian Olive Oil Industry
- 1162 *Angela Rella, Vincenzo Pontrelli, Lara Oliva, Arcangelo Marrone*
From Challenges to Opportunities: A Stakeholder Theory Approach to Circular Economy Ecosystems
- 1169 *Stefania Manetti*
Artificial Intelligence in the Agri-Food Supply Chain: How it Might Facilitate Circular Economy Practices?
- 1176 *Miriana Ferrara, Nicola Capolupo*
Unleashing Digital Transformation in LCA: The Interplay between Data-Driven Culture and Digital Capabilities
- 1183 *Michela Colacicco, Mastropasqua Antonio, Francesco Paolo Lagrasta, Barbara Scozzi*
The Role of Physical Appearance in the Entrepreneurial Journey: A State-of-the-Art Review from a Feminist Perspective
- 1192 *Tamara Menichini, Stefania Roberta Miccoli*
Exploring the Gender Gap in ERC Funding: A Geographical and Socioeconomic Analysis of Female Academic Research, Innovation, and Entrepreneurship
- 1200 *Michele Modena, Ilaria Nigro*
The Role of DAOs in Shaping Knowledge Management: Opportunities and Risks
- 1208 *Antoinette Strada, Chiara Vandoni, Guido Perboli*
Blockchain Technology and Non-Fungible Tokens (NFTs) in Museums: Legal Considerations
- 1215 *Elisa Bonacini*
Sarajevo 1992-2025: The Contribution of Art between War and Peace, Analogue and Digital
- 1225 *Maria Antonietta Cipriano, Paola Demartini*
The Human in the Loop: Artificial Intelligence as a Co-Pilot in the Creative Process of the Artists. A Critical Analysis in Visual Arts
- 1235 *Chiara Bellini, Débora Cristina De Andrade Vicente, Lucia Marchegiani*
AI for Start-up Decision-Making and Knowledge Management: Evidence from an Innovation Ecosystem
- 1243 *Gianmaria Abbondante, Alessio Di Leo, Rita Mura, Andrea De Mauro, Enzo Peruffo*
Managing in the AI Era: A Systematic Literature Review on the Evolution of Managerial Roles and Competencies

INDEX

- 1253 *Paola Demartini, Michela Marchiori, Rosa Fioravante, Flavia Marucci*
Advancing Holistic Heritage Impact Assessment through Human-Digital Collaboration
- 1263 *Elvira Tiziana La Rocca, Raffaella Coppolino*
Digital Healthcare Technologies and the Co-Design of Healthcare Services: A Scoping Review
- 1270 *Noemi Condit, Alice Ravizza*
Health Technology Assessment of Artificial Intelligence Systems: The Importance of Evaluating Digital Literacy and Trust
- 1277 *Anna Maria Melina, Rocco Reina, Raffaella Coppolino, Nadia Di Carluccio*
Healthcare Leaders in the Age of AI: New Challenges and New Opportunities
- 1284 *Antonio Bassi*
Developing a New Project Management Framework with AI, Blockchain, and Digital Twin Integration
- 1294 *Arthur Pantelides*
A Case Study in AI Integration: The Real Impact on Organizational Support, Efficiency, and Strategic Value Creation, in Global Project Management
- 1304 *Francesca Loia, Cecilia Maltempo, Rosario Marrapodi, Marcello Martinez, Stefania Mele, Mario Pezzillo Iacono*
Leveraging the Metaverse: A Multidimensional Approach to Knowledge Management in Project-Oriented Settings
- 1312 *Teresa Anna Rita Gentile, Caterina Galdiero, Paola Adinolfi, Ernesto De Nito, Gabriella Piscopo*
Hybrid Work And Knowledge Transfer In The Public Administration Context
- 1320 *Ernesto De Nito, Paolo Canonico, Andrea Caccialanza, Valentina Langella*
Knowledge Ecosystem in a Hybrid Context: Insights From a Consultancy Project
- 1326 *Paolo Canonico, Ernesto De Nito, Vincenza Esposito, Mario Pezzillo Iacono, Carla Conte*
Digital Transformation and Organizational Change in the Public Sector: Evidence from a Case Study
- 1334 *Adriana Scuotto, Paolo Canonico*
Untangling Proof-of-Concept Projects: A Systematic Literature Review
- 1346 *Giovanni Spatola, Stefania D'Aprile, Maria Zifaro, Andrea Presciutti, Alessandro Brogna*
Preliminary Study on the Impact of Artificial Intelligence in ESG Practices: A Multi-Case Approach in the Italian Market
- 1354 *Paola Campana, Riccardo Censi, Fulvio Schettino, Chiara De Pucchio*
Optimizing ESG Risk Assessment Processes with AI-Driven Process Mining: A Framework for Proactive Sustainability Management
- 1363 *Giuseppe Bruno, Manuel Cavola, Anna Del Balzo, Carmela Piccolo, Eduardo Pipicelli*
Navigating Sustainability Standards: Challenges and Interoperability Between ESRS and GRI
- 1372 *Giovanni Spatola, Giuseppe Ambrosio, Marianna Mancino, Maria Zifaro, Andrea Presciutti*
Exploring the Synergy: AI-Driven Knowledge Management, ESG Performance, and Stakeholder Perceptions in the Energy Sector
- 1379 *Marianna Mancino, Maria Zifaro, Giuseppe Ambrosio, Giovanni Spatola*
Artificial Intelligence, Knowledge Management and Reduced Work Time: Rethinking Organizational Competitiveness
- 1387 *Stefania D'Aprile, Giovanni Spatola*
Artificial Intelligence as a Driver for Educational Inclusion: Developing a Generative AI Chatbot to Support Professors and Students
- 1394 *Serena Strazzullo, Moacir Godinho Filo*
The Role of Artificial Intelligence in Social Sustainability: A Socio-Technical Systems Perspective
- 1405 *Giovanni Spatola, Mario D'Avino, Antonio Capasso, Maria Zifaro, Andrea Presciutti*
Artificial Intelligence and Social Sustainability in the Energy Sector: Enhancing Stakeholder Perception and ESG Performance through Innovative Practices
- 1412 *Marianna Mancino, Maria Zifaro, Giuseppe Ambrosio, Giovanni Spatola*
Social Taxonomy, Balance Sheet and AI for Sustainability in Public Administration Policies

INDEX

- 1421 *Viktória Papp-Horváth*
Digital Literacy of Gen Z Students in the Context of Project Management Education
- 1428 *László Berényi, Nikolett Deutsch*
Change to Digital Learning: A Task-Technology Fit Approach to Moodle
- 1436 *Roberto Mauriello, Livio Cricelli, Serena Strazzullo*
Enhancing Resilience in Agrifood Supply Chains: The Role of Technological Innovation for Risk Management
- 1445 *Stefano Marciano, Francesca Peluso*
Business Model Innovation and Digital Technologies in Agri-Food: Leveraging Boundaries for Sustainability
- 1453 *Mauro Romanelli*
Smart Responsible Innovative Cities: An Organisational Agenda
- 1458 *Raffaele Silvestre, Mauro Romanelli*
Managing Organizations between Artificial Intelligence and Technostress: A Typology Model
- 1464 *Anna Turchetta, Sara Gigli*
The Integration between Artificial Intelligence, Knowledge Management, and Collaborative Innovation for the Creation of Sustainable Value in Industry 5.0
- 1471 *Mauro Romanelli, Alexandra Zbucea, Monica Bira*
Creative Urban Spaces: A Collaborative and Organisational View
- 1476 *Fabrizio Rossi, Domenico Celenza, Elbano De Nuccio, Alessandro Sicali*
Narcissistic CEOs and Zombie Firms: Evidence from Europe
- 1484 *Giuliana Cavadi, Martina Vivoli, Federico Cosenz*
Evaluating AI's Impact in Healthcare: a Systemic Approach through Key Performance Indicators
- 1492 *Sara Consilia Papavero, Concetta Lucia Cristofaro, Rossella Di Bidino, Fabrizio Massimo Ferrara, Giuseppe Arbia, Sabrina Bonomi*
Evaluating Holistic Socio-Environmental Impact of Digital Health: Scoping Review of Decision-Making Frameworks
- 1503 *Valeria Schifilliti, Veronica Marozzo, Alessandra Costa, Augusto D'Amico*
Exploring Cardiologists' Perspectives on Wearable ECG Devices: Evidence from an E-focus Group
- 1509 *Małgorzata Runiewicz-Wardyn*
The Role of AI in Waste Reduction and Sustainability of Pharmaceutical Industry
- 1518 *Kathrin Kirchner, Ettore Bolisani, Tomas Cherkos Kassaneh, Enrico Scarso, Nima Taraghi*
Impact of Work Experience on the Use of Generative AI for Knowledge Management
- 1526 *Giuseppe Loseto, Alessandro Massaro, Giovanni Schiuma, Angelo Rosa*
Generative AI Techniques for Data Aggregation and Summarization: Enhancing Decision Support in Healthcare
- 1533 *Giuliana Barba, Marianna Lezzi, Mariangela Lazoi, Massimo Scalvenzi*
A Bibliometric Analysis of GenAI for Privacy and Information Security in Industry
- 1543 *Lucaleonardo Bove, Lorenzo Epifani, Angelo Corallo, Massimiliano Gervasi*
Harnessing Large Language Models for Data Mesh Adoption in Multi-Organizational Data Ecosystems
- 1549 *Mariasimona Miglietta, Lorenzo Epifani, Marco Di Salvo, Angelo Corallo, Gervasi Massimiliano*
Generative AI in Data Management: Enhancing Data Quality Control for Business Data
- 1557 *Francesco Filippo, Francesco Paolo Lagrasta, Stefano Lisi, Barbara Scozzi*
Individual and Organizational Factors affecting the Adoption of GenAI in Creative Contexts: an Explorative Study
- 1567 *Marco Scatto, Karen Venturini, Chiara Grosso, Alberto Petroni*
Forecasting Analysis for Technology-Driven Transition in Circular Packaging
- 1575 *Michal Krčál, Sayyed Shoaib-Ul-Hasan, Farazee Mohammad Abdullah Asif, Mikhail Monashev*
Digital Solutions to Support Transition from Linear to Circular Manufacturing
- 1582 *Tamara Menichini, Gennaro Salierno, Nicoletta Maria Strollo*
Shaping the Twin Transition: How Leading Innovators align Industry 4.0 and Circular Economy Practices for Sustainable Growth

INDEX

- 1591 *Aelita Skarzauskiene, Kristina Kovaitė, Monika Mačiulienė, Paulius Šūmakaris*
AI-driven Knowledge Futures: Digital Innovation in Cultural Heritage
- 1601 *Matias Celdrán Bonafonte, Francesco Santarsiero, Gustavo Morales-Alonso*
Transforming Hotel Innovation Management through Innovation Labs: Lessons from Spain
- 1609 *Francesco Santarsiero, Daniela Carlucci, Antonio Lerro, Rosaria Lagrutta, Vincenzo Orsi*
Assessing Digital Maturity in Rural Tourism: Insights from Pilot Areas in Basilicata
- 1615 *Antonio Lerro, Rosaria Lagrutta, Vincenzo Orsi, Francesco Santarsiero, Daniela Carlucci, Giovanna Andrulli*
Models and Tools to Support Innovation Processes in Cultural Tourism Ecosystems: Evidences and Implications for Basilicata
- 1622 *Antonio Lerro, Rosaria Lagrutta, Vincenzo Orsi, Francesco Santarsiero, Daniela Carlucci*
Digital Transformation in Rural Cultural Tourism: Insights from a SWOT Analysis in Basilicata
- 1629 *Michele Modina, Anna Vittoria Formisano, Aysan Bashirpour Bonab*
The Role of Incubators in the Innovation Ecosystem
- 1637 *Eva Panetti, Viktoriia Apalkova, Maurizio Caon*
Resilience of Entrepreneurial Ecosystems (EEs) in Switzerland: Diversity, Coherence, and Digitalization
- 1645 *Antonio Sonetto, Silvia Tommaso, Antonio Ricciardi*
Leveraging External Knowledge: How Business Incubators Facilitate Open Innovation in Start-ups
- 1653 *Laura Monferdini, Benedetta Pini, Virginia Dolci, Eleonora Bottani*
How Emerging Technologies Drive Collaboration in Start-Ups' Innovation Ecosystems
- 1661 *Serena Filippelli, Barbara Bigliardi, Virginia Dolci, Laura Monferdini, Benedetta Pini*
The Impact of Digitalization and Open Innovation on the Performance of Innovative Startups: A Systematic Literature Review
- 1670 *Barbara Bigliardi, Benedetta Pini, Virginia Dolci, Alberto Petroni, Sara Guareschi*
Enabling and Hindering Factors in the Collaboration Between Startups and Big Enterprises within Innovation Ecosystems: A Focus on Sustainability and Digitization
- 1680 *Maria Cristina Pietronudo, Eva Panetti, Andrea Caporuscio, Daniele Leone*
Mental Models for Entrepreneurial Ecosystems: A Simulation Experiment
- 1687 *Alberto Michele Felicetti, Salvatore Ammirato, Roberto Linzalone, Laura Cutri*
Orchestrating Digital Innovation Ecosystems: A Case Study on Asymmetric Collaborations in Pharma Logistics
- 1696 *Filomena Riemma, Davide de Gennaro, Filomena Buonocore, Rosario Marrapodi*
Stress Management and Organizational Strategies: Promoting Well-Being and Innovation in Healthcare Systems
- 1704 *Alice Mannocci, Guendalina Capece, David Shaholli, Jessica Prataviera, Lombardo Floranna Guarente, Ilaria Frantellizzi, Ramos Mren Quesada, Francesco Belsito, Bruno Gerace, Ginevra Duraturo, Claudia Sarcoli, Antonietta Monteduro, Giuseppe La Torre*
A Randomized Controlled Field Trial: A Gamified Training Course on Workplace Health and Safety Prevention for Middle School Students – "Let's Play 81!"
- 1709 *Cristina Cersosimo, Franco Ernesto Rubino*
The Role of Digital Technologies on Corporate Governance Mechanisms
- 1717 *Riccardo Michele Colangelo, Eleonora Petrazzuoli, Maria Menshikova, Vito Saverio Cicoira, Nunzia Cosmo*
Costs and Benefits of AI Adoption in the Recruitment Process: Organisational, Recruiter, and Job Applicant Perspectives
- 1727 *Leonio Capparelli, Lapo Biancardi, Michele Galeotti, Vincenzo Scafarto*
Digital Transformation, Board of Directors and Environmental Performance: Evidence from Italian Listed Companies
- 1734 *Giacomo Gotti, Angela Oksana Fiorella, Carla Morrone, Valerio D'Ovidio*
Navigating Sustainable Corporate Governance in the Age of Artificial Intelligence: Primary Evidence from Italy
- 1740 *Daniela Cicchini, Paolo Conte, Luana Pellegrini*
Digitalization and Sustainability Reporting in the Public Sector: A Structured Literature Review

INDEX

- 1750 *Giovanna Muraglia, Laura Clemente, Gesualda Iodice, Mariavittoria Cicellin, Francesco Bifulco*
Digital Transformation and Public-Private Partnerships to Enhance Local Cultural Heritage
- 1758 *Fabio Greco, Francesco Bifulco*
Measuring Museum Visitor Experience: Fresh Evidence from Bourbon Heritage Sites and potential Collaborations with Startups
- 1766 *Chiara Vandoni, Guido Perboli*
Barriers to Web3 Technologies in Museums: A Qualitative Study in Turin
- 1775 *Amelia Napolitano, Laura Clemente, Francesco Bifulco*
Artificial Intelligence and Value Co-creation in Museums: Promoting Inclusion for People With Disabilities
- 1783 *Jean-Baptiste Philippe*
Redefining Middle Management: How Generative AI Reshapes Roles and Competencies
- 1793 *Gianluca Gherardi*
A (Fun)Nel Model for Knowledge Management
- 1797 *Matteo Barisone, Diana Rolando, Alice Barreca, Concetta Sulpizio*
AI-Driven Data Integration in Real Estate Development Processes
- 1806 *Heini Merkkiniemi*
Let Me Entertain You: Managing Socially Sustainable Experience Economy Ecosystems
- 1812 *Sandra Penger, Vlado Dimovski, Maja Meško, Judita Peterlin, Vasja Roblek*
The Use of Artificial Intelligence in Recruitment Selection in Slovenian Organisations: An Exploratory Approach
Analysing HR Managers' Experiences
- 1817 *Lufuno Lugisani, Oluseye Jegede*
The Role of Chatbots in Enhancing Managerial Experience within Organisations
- 1826 *Petia Genkova, Henrik Schreiber, Edwin Semke*
Global or Local Player? – Cultural Diversity and Barriers in STEM Studies
- 1835 *Maja Bacović*
A Country's Innovativeness as a Determinant of Income Convergence
- 1842 *Behrooz Moradi, Ettore Bolisani, Juan-Gabriel Cegarra-Navarro, Aurora Martínez Martínez, Tomas Cherkos Kassaneh, Furong Cai*
Towards a Unified Framework for Knowledge Worker Roles: A Systematic Literature Review
- 1852 *Micol Di Vita, Emilio Paolucci, Elisabetta Raguseo*
Do Mentors Influence the Effects of the Entrepreneurial Programs of Early-Stage Start-Ups Pivot Decisions? An RCT Experiment
- 1858 *Alfredo Castro, Roberto Sbragia, Elza Veloso*
Digital Leadership in the Era of Remote Work: Challenges, Strategies, and the impact of AI
- 1866 *Roberto Grandinetti*
How Artificial Intelligence Erodes the Tacit Dimension of Organizations
- 1872 *Ewa Stolarek-Muszyńska, Malgorzata Zieba*
Navigating Uncertainty through Knowledge Sharing: Lessons from Tourism in Times of Pandemic. Case Study from Poland
- 1878 *Igor Zatsman*
AI Technology for Language Knowledge Discovery Built on Modified Spiral Model and DIK Hierarchy
- 1888 *Riccardo Ventura, Ilaria Mariani*
Open Innovation for Virtual Worlds: A Design-Driven Theoretical Framework for the Creation of User-Generated Experiences
- 1899 *Ludovica Nardi, Andrea De Mauro*
Managing Prices in the Age of AI: A Taxonomy of AI Applications to Support Pricing Decisions
- 1906 *Amarildo Zane, Fátima Guadamillas Gómez, Mario Javier Donate Manzanares*
Knowledge Management in Diverse Organizations: A Meta-Data Analysis

INDEX

- 1917 *Carlo Drago, Francesca Valentina Giglio Moro, Angelo Leogrande*
Bibliometric Ensemble-Based Community Detection Analysis of AI, Knowledge Management, and Emerging Technologies Convergence in Business Paradigms
- 1922 *Martyna Skorupko, Malgorzata Zieba*
Employee Withdrawal and Knowledge Management Processes
- 1929 *Claude Meier, Ursula Häfliger*
Generative Artificial Intelligence: Knowledge, Perception and Use among White-Collar Employees in Companies
- 1939 *Marco Praticò, Salvatore Tallarico, Luisa Pellegrini, Simone Lazzini*
Improving Clinical Evidence for Medical Devices: A Lifecycle Approach
- 1947 *Gustavo Morales-Alonso, Faisal Rasool, Yulissa Navarro-Castillo, Antonio Hidalgo*
Exploring Frugal and Reverse Innovation: A Bibliometric Review and Conceptual Proposal
- 1955 *Ranieri Alves dos Santos, Fernando Alvaro Ostuni Gauthier, Marcelo Macedo, Vanessa Roberg*
The Use of Generative AI and Lean UX in Knowledge Engineering Projects
- 1961 *Stefano Abbate, Piera Centobelli, Maria Di Gregorio*
Food Waste Valorisation: A Comparative Study with a Hybrid AHP-Fuzzy Approach
- 1967 *Fiengo Vincenzo, Passaro Renato, Quinto Ivana*
A Framework for Assessing the Sustainability of P2P Platforms
- 1975 *Giovanni Baldissarro, Gianpaolo Iazzolino, Giuseppe Longo, Donato Morea*
Innovation in Entrepreneurship and Performance: An Empirical Research on Italian Innovative Startups
- 1984 *Mirva Hyypiä*
Meaningfulness Reshaping Technology, Knowledge Co-Creation, and Leadership
- 1992 *Tamara Menichini, Gennaro Salierno, Nicoletta Maria Strollo*
Materiality Analysis for SDG Prioritization: Is Multi-Criteria Decision Making Helpful?
- 1999 *Fabrizio Baldassarre, Savino Santovito, Raffaele Campo, Pierfelice Rosato*
Enhancing the Acceptation of Insects as Food: A Sustainable Strategy?
- 2004 *Dijana Oreski*
Enhancing Organizational Knowledge Management through Retrieval-Augmented Generation and Large Language Models
- 2010 *Daniela Sica, Benedetta Esposito, Stefania Supino*
Integrating GPT Models into Life Cycle Assessment: Unlocking Artificial Intelligence-Driven Circular Economy
- 2019 *Panus Faroongsarng, Pornthipa Ongkunaruk*
Improving Revenue and Delivery Performance by Production Planning Using Mixed Integer Programming in a Plastic Manufacturing Industry
- 2026 *Wuttipong Panitsettakorn, Pornthipa Ongkunaruk, Thaweephan Leingpibul*
Trust, Transparency, and Technology: A Case Study of IQAV-Driven Quality Assurance in Thailand's Cosmetic Sector

Sarajevo 1992-2025: The Contribution of Art between War and Peace, Analogue and Digital

Elisa Bonacini

University of Bari "Aldo Moro", Bari, Italy

Abstract

To celebrate the anniversary of the Dayton agreements after the Sarajevo war (1992-1995), a phygital exhibition *Sarajevo 1995-2025. From war to peace on the thirtieth anniversary of the Dayton Peace Agreement* is going to be launched between Bari and Sarajevo, inspired by the *Ars Aevi project* and celebrated through words and experiences of many protagonists, from local to Italian authorities, from children of yesterday to the adults of today.

Born as a political and peaceful artistic action in response to the war, conceived and realized by Enver 'Enjo' Hadžiomerspahić, the project started in 1992 from the Michelangelo Pistoletto's donation of his artwork *Porta allo Specchio*. Become one of the greatest contemporary art collections, *Ars Aevi* will find its definitive location in the new Museum of Contemporary Art designed by Renzo Piano in 2005, donated to Sarajevo and just presented according to its executive design. The collection can be known and enjoyed thanks to the website, the online catalogue and a virtual exhibition, a sort of demo preview of the new Sarajevo Museum.

The project of the *Sarajevo 1995-2025* exhibition, realized through the collaboration of the University of Bari "Aldo Moro", many Italian and Bosnian institutions and the partnership of the Ars Aevi Museum, aims to promote intercultural dialogue and peace, through an exhibition combining stories and contents, in a physical, digital, interactive and immersive way, by using different digital tools, such as an interactive 'augmented' catalogue and a VR exhibition on ArtSteps.

Keywords: Digital Art History, VR experiences, Phygital exhibitions, VR exhibitions, Virtual environments.

Paper type: Academic Research Paper

1 The Ars Aevi project as an inspiring ideal and value-based model for contemporary art and peace building processes

Before introducing the *Sarajevo 1995-2025. From war to peace on the thirtieth anniversary of the Dayton Peace Agreement* exhibition, a premise is required, necessary to describe what happened under the bombings, starting from 1992, and in the following decades. In the peacebuilding process, contemporary art was an essential protagonist: the *Sarajevo 1995-2025* exhibition got inspired from the *Ars Aevi project*, as an ideal and value-based source for the project itself which will be inaugurated in Bari in autumn 2025.

The anagram itself of the project, a logo embracing the name of Sarajevo like a *tai*, represents *Ars Aevi's* ethical-visual identity, in a perpetual and progressive balance between contrasting forces. *Art of an era crossing the limits of time*: this is the meaning of the Latin expression, chosen as a (partial) graphical anagram of Sarajevo, described on the website collecting the history of the collection, born as a political and peaceful act in response to the war (fig. 1).

In 1992, faced with the horrors of war and the siege of Sarajevo, culture and art were used as true instruments of resistance (Caira and Cavigioli 2021). Contemporary art was called to contribute in a peace-message building, in a collective and participatory way, to a visionary and long-term project launched by Enver 'Enjo' Hadžiomerspahić, former director of the Biennale Jugoslovenska Dokumenta in Sarajevo (1987-89), together with other Bosnian intellectuals and artists. Over the last thirty years since the beginning of the Bosnian war, this call to the arts shaped a very rich collection (over 160 works), the *Ars Aevi Museum of Contemporary art*, which is coming to a definition of its own physical and definitive museum space, after its "nomadic and itinerant dimension" (Azzerboni 2023).

Figure 1: Homepage of the Ars Aevi website.

32 years later, 'Enjo' himself left testimony of his initiative, which he led until 2017 (replaced in 2018 as Ars Aevi Director by Senka Ibrišimbegović, University of Sarajevo, which is partner of our initiative), in a long interview to Franco Giuliano, reporter during the war for the *Gazzetta del Mezzogiorno* newspaper and creator of the *Sarajevo 1995-2025* exhibition. Hundreds of artists from all over the world transformed Sarajevo into a multicultural capital of art and the art collection itself into a universal message of the value of art from a moral and aesthetic point of view, as declared in the manifesto of Ars Aevi Museum on the website: *Art can overcome evil and destruction. Culture is the mother of tolerance. Intercultural dialogue enriches. The universal language of art unites.*

Just at the beginning of the siege of Sarajevo (June 1992), when it was *crazy* thinking about art under bombings, the idea of 'Enjo' was immediately embraced by the city of Sarajevo itself and by the Bosnia-Herzegovina State as a long-term project (under its first name *Sarajevo 2000*), immediately revealed as an innovative model and a unicum for participation and vertical cooperation between artists, museums, centres and foundations of contemporary art from all over the world (MIMEH 1999). The 45th Venice Biennale, in 1993, was the occasion to present its concept to the world. Thanks to Enrico Comi - the artistic director of the Sarajevo 2000 project by founding the "Spazio Umano/Human Space" Contemporary Art Centre in Milan -, Michelangelo Pistoletto's exhibition in 1994 was the first response to that call: his *Porta allo Specchio*, dating 1989 (fig. 2) started the collection (Hadžiomerspahić 2005; *Ars Aevi* 2009; Comi 2015, pp. 19-21; Carolo 2016; Webber 2018; Azzerboni 2023).

Thanks to many Italian institutions, the voice of art soon made itself heard with great power as a manifestation of resilience against that war and every war, as never before in our contemporary times. The answer of the most famous artists - from Kounellis to Kosuth, from Accardi to Abramovich, from Kapoor to Viola, just to name a few - was not long in coming and the curators of the institutions called to select the works became over the years co-founders of the project, which therefore had a unique museogenesis. From 1994 until 2012, the creation of this collection was the focus of specific exhibitions/donations, organized by museums, centres and foundations of contemporary art, such as those of Milan (Spazio Umano, 1994), Prato (Centro Pecci, 1996, to whose curator Bruno Corà we owe the invention of the anagram of the project, called *Ars Aevi 2000*), Ljubljana (Moderna Galerija, 1996-97), Venice (Biennale; Querini Stampalia and Bevilacqua La Masa foundations, 1997), Vienna (Museum moderner Kunst Stiftung Ludwig, 1998), Bolognano (Paradise Museum in the estate of Lucrezia de Domizio Durini, 2003), Istanbul (BM Contemporary Art Centre, 2007) and Podgorica (Centre for Contemporary Art of Montenegro, 2012), thus forming the various *nuclei* of the collection, to which is added the nucleus of Sarajevo itself, formed thanks to a series of personal exhibitions (1994-2006). In 2023, Ars Aevi Nucleus Kyiv have been created as an expression of solidarity with Ukraine, according to its mission in peacebuilding. After an initial exile condition, hosted by different exhibition venues and in turn a widespread instrument of cultural resistance, in 1999 'Enjo' decided to set up an exhibition at the Centar Skenderija in Sarajevo: a historic event for the art world, with the first 105 artworks (installations, paintings, sculptures, photographs). Due to the most innovative moral value in the world, this museological approach since 1999 have been recognized and supported by UNESCO and its Goodwill Ambassador, the architect Renzo Piano.

Since 2019, the collection is temporarily housed at the Vijećnica, the seat of the Sarajevo Municipality, one of the symbols of a war (the National and University Library before the siege), deliberately not spared from incendiary bombs, cannon fire, grenades, rebuilt in 1996-2014.

The Ars Aevi collection, presented in an online catalogue on the website (the only place where the entire collection is described so far: <http://www.arsaevi.ba>), will find its definitive location in the new Museum, presented by Renzo Piano in 2005, updated in 2012, donated to the City of Sarajevo and financed in its executive design by the Italian Agency and by a crowdfunding launched in collaboration with UNESCO. Already in 2002, Renzo Piano donated a new pedestrian bridge, connecting the two banks of the Miljacka river to allow access to the area where the Museum will be built, where the white and blue flags of Daniel Buren's installation, *La Place des drapeaux* still stand. Here, on 20 August 2024, the first stone of the new Museum has been laid, realizing Piano's design idea (fig. 3).

Figure 2: The first artist for the Ars Aevi collection (from the Ars Aevi Picture book).

Figure 3: Rendering of the Museum of Contemporary Art ARS AEVI project by Studio Nonstop (Sarajevo), designed by Renzo Piano Building Workshop (@Studsononstop).

2 The Sarajevo 1995-2025. From war to peace on the thirtieth anniversary of the Dayton Peace Agreement phigital exhibition

The web offers the *Ars Aevi* collection the opportunity to be known and enjoyed in its entirety, thanks to the website, the catalogue with the artworks' descriptions and the virtual exhibition that 3D reproduces the spaces designed by Renzo Piano, a sort of interactive demo of the new Sarajevo Museum (figs. 4-5), surrounded by *La Place des drapeaux* Buren's installation, symbolically marking the Terrain of the Future Museum of Contemporary Art, since 1996.

Figure 4: The Ars Aevi virtual exhibition.

Figure 5: The Ars Aevi virtual exhibition.

To tell the story of the *Sarajevo 1995-2025* exhibition, the University of Bari staff and the DABIMUS digital university lab directed by Nicola Barbuti decided to use different digital tools, expanding the physical exhibition in content and space, such as an interactive augmented catalogue, whose contents are hosted in a special mobile application, EXEBook, developed and owned by DABIMUS (Barbuti and De Bari 2022), and an exhibition on ArtSteps, a free platform for building virtual exhibitions, which will be better described in this paper.

Starting from the images of the devastated urban landscape, from the letters that the children of Sarajevo wrote to their peers in Puglia, from the testimonies of the many protagonists, who populate the virtual rooms of the exhibition, a special place is occupied by the *Ars Aevi* collection immersive story.

The process, which guided the choices regarding the exhibition, led the curator Franco Giuliano and the University of Bari and DABIMUS staff to proceed with the digitization of all the archive and photographic material related to the years in which Giuliano was sent in Bosnia for the *Gazzetta del Mezzogiorno*, during the Balkans war. On that occasion, in addition to recounting that event on the Italian press, Giuliano collected and published on the newspaper dozens of letters written by the children of the Catholic School of Sarajevo, involving prominent Italian and Bosnian personalities of the time. "Sarajevo calls Puglia" was the title of the newspaper's initiative, inviting readers to send gifts to the Bosnian children.

The concept of the exhibition revolves around the photographic documentation, news and life of the people and the city of Sarajevo, created through those letters/messages that in 1995 students entrusted to Giuliano and were translated and published in *La Gazzetta del Mezzogiorno*, to which many children from Puglia answered by sending gifts that were brought with a special mission. Those testimonies, letters and newspaper pages from Sarajevo, together with other important documents, can now tell, after 30 years, what the War in the Balkans was and what the Balkans are today. Some of those children, now adults, were interviewed and

involved 30 years later to document how much and how the war affected and still affects their lives. The wounds of the soul are then combined with the wounds that the landscape has suffered through the destruction of symbolic monuments of the city. In fact, Sarajevo's cultural heritage was also heavily involved during the war in the former Yugoslavia: cultural and religious sites were destroyed or seriously damaged and the city's urban landscape itself shows holes, cracks and gashes that still recall wounds that seem incurable.

The exhibition, in its physical and virtual version, wants to document these events through photographic augmented panels which refer to digital content of various types: newspaper articles, letters, photographs, video-testimonies, audio content, also linked to the expanded exhibition catalogue, developed by DABIMUS through their specific EXEBook application and AI tools, such as Genially (used both as backend to host mapped resources with original objects and environments, and to build interactive learning and communication materials), and by the writer, to a VR exhibition on ArtSteps, where a selection of the digitized content are displayed.

3 From SecondLife to ArtSteps, Virtual Reality Platforms and the *Sarajevo 1995-2025 VR Exhibition*

The use of virtual environments to foster new forms of connection and engagement with art has entered common practice, thanks to its high educational, interactive and informative potential. Since the end of the 1990s and in the first half of the 2000s, the first entirely virtual museums and full immersion platforms such as Second Life (a MUVE, *on-line multi-user virtual environment*) revealed their potential for new cultural learning processes in a collective space, in which multiple users interact simultaneously (Bonacini 2011).

Created in 2003 before Facebook and defined as a proto-metaverse system, SL is the true forerunner of the metaverse launched by Meta, an essential starting point for any discussion on the topic of virtual environments (Calveri 2023). On SL, in 2007, the Royal Gallery of Dresden virtually recreated the original disposition of the paintings, as they appeared in the *Gallery of the Old Masters* around 1750. In Italy, in the meantime, we were witnessing the innovative *SLAssisi project*, the digital recreation of the Basilica of St. Francis of Assisi, damaged by the 1997 earthquake, and accessible on the web in an immersive mode through head-up displays, derived from the world of immersive gaming, whose replicability in the cultural sphere was then beginning to be tested (Bonacini 2011). It is no coincidence, therefore, that between 2007 and 2011 SL hosted the *Metaverse Museum* project, which for years displayed digital art exhibitions, created exclusively in this parallel virtual world; then moved to *Craft World Opensim* and, in 2023, opened to artists' creativity until landing on Spatial platform in 2023. The case of the *Metaverse Museum* itself is clear proof of how the creation of artistic spaces in virtual worlds is a practice much further away in time, digitally speaking, than one might think.

Virtuality can therefore be considered one of the answers that modern technology provided regarding the role that communication had to play as an intrinsic function of the work of art, to avoid denying or prejudicing the artistic experience itself, if not in its full authenticity, at least in its potential for articulation and connections (Ragghianti 1974; Pietroni, Pagano and Fanini 2018). Almost given up for dead, SL has seen a relaunch and a total restyling over the last few years; then, favoured by the pandemic for the opportunity of creating virtual educational environments, it still boasts thousands of active virtual scenarios today, including artistic experiences, such as the VR version of the MoMA (fig. 6) and the Vordun Museum and Gallery, a virtual museum created on SL in July 2016 and updated to date with numerous exhibits created through reproductions of works of art in the public domain (fig. 7), equipped with descriptive audio guides and working in immersive mode. Since March 2023, SL has also launched its beta-version for mobile devices on app stores.

Figure 6: The MoMA virtual gallery on Second Life.

Figure 7: The European Masters gallery in the Vordun Museum and Gallery on Second Life.

After more than twenty years, virtual experiences have confirmed their great potential both in the communication and enjoyment of art, and in engagement with the public, thanks to the implementation of interactive solutions and communication models based on a storytelling approaches (Bonacini 2023). In this panorama, virtual museums are to be considered places where an experience of artistic perception can be recreated, stimulating wonder through the creation of a multimedia and multisensory environment to trigger a creative process useful for directing, internalizing and assimilating the understanding of historical content (De Vincentis 2023).

Among the web platforms available (in addition to Spatial, it is enough to mention Kunstmatrix, CoSpaces, ArtPlacer or Curat1On), ArtSteps is one of the most highly versatile in creating three-dimensional spaces easily and intuitively navigable (Parson 2023; Vital et al. 2023); therefore, especially after the lockdown, it has been used for virtual projects of an educational and informative nature (Fokides and Sfakianou 2017; Cruz and Torres 2022; Dell'Utri 2002; Garbui and Pellizzari 2022; Piva 2023), for virtual exhibitions produced by museums and cultural institutions (Dell'Utri 2022; Leonardi and Bonacini 2024), or for immersive digital art portfolios, created by digital artists or art galleries. In general, tools such as ArtSteps are skilful in transforming art presentation and visualization solutions, even in participatory and collaborative ways, allowing experimental decision-making and creative-thinking activities, in the context of the virtualization of the historical-artistic experience.

In addition, platforms such as ArtSteps allow experimentation with digital and virtual curation solutions. This is certainly one of the most innovative activities that a *digital art historian* can undertake, from a creative and scientific point of view, as it is one of the areas of greatest experimentation that digital revolution introduced into museological and museographic practices.

3.1 The Sarajevo 1995-2025 VR exhibition on ArtSteps

The *Sarajevo 1995-2025 VR exhibition* (<https://www.artsteps.com/view/67ead8dca81e5737cc3427c2>) is the virtual and immersive version of the story told through the other media, the physical exhibition and the interactive catalogue with its application, in Italian and Bosnian languages.

To create the virtual exhibition, it was decided not to use a pre-existing template, but to design the spaces taking advantage of the full potential of the virtual exhibition surface, available by the ArtSteps system itself, corresponding to approximately 1300 square meters (a maximum of 36 meters per side). From a design point of view, the creative process was therefore developed in a series of intuitive steps, from the creation of the exhibition space to its planning through visual (photos, videos) and narrative (captions, audio descriptions) content. Original photos, videos, newspaper pages were all digitized by DABIMUS staff. In this case, the textual contents of the articles, transcribed in Italian and translated into Bosnian by Maurizio De Bari and the DABIMUS staff were interpreted in Italian by the students of the Digital Valorisation of Museum Collection course at the University of Bari, while those in Bosnian by nuns and students at the Catholic School of Sarajevo. CABOLO® AI-based solution have been used for speech-to-text transcription, translation and subtitling all the video interviews (as a form of sponsorship for the phygital exhibition by the Cedat 85 firm).

The visit route was designed with an introductory environment, in which the entire exhibition is presented (the graphics of which were created as a thesis project by Alessia Cioce, a student of the Digital Heritage specialistic degree course at the University of Bari), and four rooms that lead the virtual visitor on the narrative path.

The first room, *Sarajevo, the war and the Dayton Agreement in 1995*, is dedicated to the visual and documentary framing of the last months of the war until the signing of the agreements that put an end to four years of conflict. Original parts of a video-documentary, realized for the Italian television in December 1995, and the photographic repertoire of war correspondent Franco Giuliano, have been used with photos collected through other witnesses, such as the commander of the Italian contingent in Sarajevo, general Pedone, and the press review, which recounts the turbulent moments that then led to peace.

The second room, entitled *Ars Aevi. Art as Peace Instrument*, is an artistic tribute, thirty years later, to the great project launched by Enver 'Enjo' Hadžiomerspahić in the aftermath of the outbreak of the War (fig. 8). Thanks to the full collaboration of the Ars Aevi Museum, in the persons of its director Senka Ibrišimbegović and her staff, we were able to select the works to be digitally exhibited within the entire digitized collection. In this way, space was left for a real "exhibition within the exhibition", characterized by a specific digital curatorship, which guided the artworks choice. This section is immediately introduced by the *Ars Aevi*'s anagram and two short videos, in Italian subtitled in Bosnian language, in which Enjo recounts the birth and development of his creature, which has become a manifestation of the resilience of global culture against that war and every war. It was decided to highlight 4 or at most 5 works from the same nucleus, starting from the oldest (Milan 1994) and Michelangelo Pistoletto's artwork (fig. 9), ending with the Podgorica collections (2012). Each section is introduced by the name of the collection and an interactive image (accompanied by a short audio description in Italian, with the writer's voiceover, and in Bosnian language, with Senka Ibrišimbegović's voiceover) taken from the *Picture Book*, which briefly indicates the number and name of the artists who participated in that specific exhibition and the name of the curator who was responsible for its selection [starting with Enrico Comi (partner of the *Sarajevo Biennale* and the true driving force behind the project in Italy, who was the artistic director of the *Sarajevo 2000* project and the founder of the "Spazio Umano/Human Space" Contemporary Art Centre in Milan) and by the Centro Pecci in Prato (to whose curator Bruno Corà we owe the invention of the *Ars Aevi 2000*)]. Among the more than 160 digitized images, artworks were deliberately selected, as they would allow users to read linked-themes such as life and death, precariousness, passage, human connections, desires. The stuffed ducklings in the photo by Ingeborg Lüscher (1998) or the brave teddy bear by Dimitri Prigrov (1998) cannot help but recall the small "desiderata" of Bosnian children in their letters. The *Hanged Man* by Juan Muñoz (1988) simultaneously recalls Bill Viola's video installation, *The Passing* (1991), and Nan Golden's photograph, *Bruce in the Ruins, Pompei* (1995). Tony Cragg's installation *Quarry* (1990), in which a crane is surrounded by a series of cement bags, reminds us a machine gun post, linking on the one hand to Jan Håfström's tragically ironic installation *Holiday Inn, Sarajevo* (1997), with its façade built from jute bags and wood; on the other to Marjetica Potrč's installation *A House With a Room for Possessions* (1999) or Nebojša Šerić's photograph of a soldier in a trench (1998), from the Viennese nucleus. The selection of the three works from the Vienna collection gives us an even more powerful meaning, with Andrés Compagnucci's *Gonzo* offering a bunch of coloured flowers, a sign of peace, the blood-red hammer and sickle by Sándor Pinczehelyi (1973) and, again, the soldier in the trench by Nebojša Šerić (fig. 10).

In the third room, *Sarajevo calls Puglia*, letters and press reviews tell users the great humanitarian event that involved children from both sides of the Adriatic sea, thanks to the initiative promoted by the *Gazzetta del Mezzogiorno*, through its reporter Franco Giuliano. He firstly collected letters from Bosnian children to send to Italy, and collected reply letters from all Puglia region, involving children and their families. In those weeks, between December 1995 and January 1996, hundreds of letters travelled between the two opposite coasts of the sea. Then, Giuliano arranged the much-desired gifts delivery, thanks to a mission organized by the then Minister of Defense Andreatta. Bosnian and Italian letters have been selected to be exhibited in this virtual route, transcribed into the corresponding languages and translated. The letters' voiceover was made by children from the same schools involved at the time, the Catholic School in Sarajevo and a local school in Bari; the newspaper's voiceover by students from the University of Bari.

In the end, the last section, *Testimonies between war and peace*, collects videointerviews of some of the protagonists of those events, in two languages and subtitled in Italian or Bosnian.

Figure 8: Sarajevo 1995-2025 VR exhibition on ArtSteps. The ARS AEVI Museum of Contemporary Art of Sarajevo section.

Figure 9: Sarajevo 1995-2025 VR exhibition on ArtSteps. Michelangelo Pistoletto's "Porta dello Specchio", Milan Collection.

Figure 10: Sarajevo 1995-2025 VR exhibition on ArtSteps. A panorama of the virtual tour with the Sarajevo, the Wien and the Bolognano collections.

4 Conclusions

The *Sarajevo 1995-2025 VR exhibition* is a demonstration of how these virtual spaces are open to creativity and design, a place where Digital art-historians and Digital curators could develop their new digital and virtual skills, by curating virtual exhibition and itineraries, as real curated pathways (De Vincentis 2023). This virtual project, created through the digitalization of analog contents and the use of AI tools, has its true core in the participation in telling stories, in reading newspaper articles and letters, trying to return, in a digital and virtual way, the same collaborative spirit that both the *Ars Aevi* initiative had, for the world of art, and the *Sarajevo calls Puglia* one, from an humanitarian point of view.

5 Acknowledgements

The project falls within the European project ‘Cultural Heritage Active Innovation for Sustainable Society - CHANGES’ code n. PE00000020 - CUP: H53C22000860006. We would like to thank Franco and Enrica Giuliano for their collaboration in identifying the archive and photographic material that could be reused for the physical and virtual exhibition; Nicola Barbuti, Maurizio De Bari and the DABIMUS staff for the digitization of all the material provided, for the transcription and translation of the articles of the *Gazzetta del Mezzogiorno* and the letters of the Bosnian and Italian children; Senka Ibrišimbegović and her staff from the *Ars Aevi* project, for having accepted the proposal of a virtual collaboration at a distance to give visibility to the contemporary art collection of Sarajevo; PierLuigi Mirizzi and the Media Division Group to let us reuse archival content from *Gazzetta del Mezzogiorno*; Alessia Cioce for the graphic design of the exhibition; the group of the Department of Audiovisual, music and performance disciplines of the University of Bari (Federico Zecca, Angela Saponari, Francesco Dongiovanni) for their collaboration in editing the video interviews; the nuns and students of the Catholic School of Sarajevo for collaborating in the revision of the translations and the voice-over of the texts in Bosnian; the students of the Digital Valorization of Museum Collections course at the University of Bari.

6 Ethics declaration

The writer has been authorized by the *Ars Aevi* museum, partner of the project, for the publication of the images on ArtSteps.

7 AI declaration

No AI tool have been used in developing this paper.

References

- Ars Aevi Museum of Contemporary Art Sarajevo Exhibition and Catalogue (2009), 53rd Venice Biennale. Ca' Pesaro, Venice, Sarajevo
- Azzerboni, M. (2023) ARS AEVI. Storia di un museo in esilio, Thesis (2022-23), Bologna University.
- Baca, M. Helmreich, A. and Rodríguez Ortega, N. (2013) "Digital Art History", *Visual Resources*, Vol. 29, No. 1-2.
- Barbuti, N., De Bari Maurizio (2022), "Addressing User Engagement With an Interactive Reading Model by Innovative Digital Expansion", *IRCDL 2022: 18th Italian Research Conference on Digital Libraries* (February 24–25, 2022, Padova, Italy).
- Bonacini, E. (2011) Nuove tecnologie per la fruizione e valorizzazione del patrimonio culturale, Aracne Editrice, Roma.
- Bonacini, E. (2023) Museums and Forms of Digital Storytelling, Aracne Editrice, Roma.
- Caira, A. and Caviglioli, A. (2021) La resistenza oltre alle armi. Sarajevo 1992-1996, Mimesis Edizioni, Sesto San Giovanni.
- Calveri, C. (2023) Metaversi culturali. Nuove frontiere digitali per le imprese e la cultura, Editrice Bibliografica, Milano.
- Cameron, F. (2021) The Future of Digital Data, Heritage and Curation in a More-than-Human world, Routledge, London.
- Carolo, S.M. (2016) Narrating Ars Aevi. Re-envisioning and Re-shaping the Contemporary Art Museum of Sarajevo in the Urban Space, Thesis (2015-16), Venezia Ca' Foscari University.
- Comi, E. (2015) "The Contemporary Art Centre "Spazio Umano/Human Space" ...when the impossible becomes possible...", International Magazine Book of Arts and Cultures Human Space, January 2015.
- Cruz, S. and Torres, A. (2022) "Virtual and immersive learning environments using art steps: exploratory study with teachers", Proceedings of the International Conferences e-Learning, Lisbon, pp. 165-168
- Dell'Utri, C. (2022) "REWIND, 10 anni al Museo Diocesano di Monreale" – Nuovi scenari di fruizione digitale per i musei dopo la pandemia, *Osservatorio per le Arti Decorative in Italia*, No. 26, pp. 115-130.
- De Vincentis, S. (2023) Il Museo digitale. Esperienze e progetti, Editori Paparo, Roma
- Fokides, E. and Sfakianou, M. (2017) "Virtual Museums in Arts Education. Results of a Pilot Project in Primary School Settings", *Asian Research Journal of Arts & Social Sciences*, Vol. 3, No. 1, pp. 1-10.
- Garbui, M.C. and Pelizzari, F. (2022) "Artsteps. Un'esperienza di progettazione culturale e virtuale", *Atti Didamatica*, Milano, pp. 202-209.
- Hadžiomerspahić, E. (2005) Facts, Appunti per un racconto su Ars Aevi, Vol. 1, Sarajevo.
- Han, H.C. (2017) "Virtual World and Creativity", *Journal of Virtual Studies*, Vol. 8, No. 2, pp. 11-22.
- Impett, L. and Offert, F. (2023) "There Is a Digital Art History", *arXiv*, No. 2308.07464
- Kayaalp, F., Namli, Z.B. and Meral, E. (2024) "My museum: A study of pre-service social studies teachers' experience in designing virtual museums", *Education and Information Technologies*.
- Leonardi, A., Bonacini, E. (2024) "Michelangelo su ArtSteps. L'esperienza VR di Michelangelo antifascista a Bari", in Michelangelo antifascista a Bari (1964-1965) Il 'non finito' di Adriano Prandi e il critofilm di Carlo Ludovico Ragghianti nel IV centenario della scomparsa del Buonarroti, ed. A. Leonardi, Bari, pp. 225-240.
- MIMEH: Modelli innovativi di management di musei e beni culturali in Europa, Torino (2009), pp. 16-18.
- Parsons, A. (2023) "Virtual Art Galleries as Learning Spaces and Agents of Praxis", *AI, Computer Science and Robotics Technology*, Vol. 2, pp. 1-23.
- Pietroni, E., Pagano, A., and Fanini, B. (2018) "UX Designer and Software Developer at the Mirror: Assessing Sensory Immersion and Emotional Involvement in Virtual Museums", *Studies in Digital Heritage*, Vol. 2, No. 1, pp. 13-41.
- Piva, M. (2023) "Virtual tour e didattica immersiva: creazione di un museo virtuale-interattivo nella scuola primaria", *Open Journal of IUL University*, Vol. 4, No. 7, pp. 312-327.
- Purnamasari, I., Azhari, I. and Amelia, P. (2023) "Development of a Museum Virtual Tour Based on the Art Steps Application of the Lae Meang Old Tomb Site, Pakpak Bharat, Indonesia", *International Journal of Computer Applications Technology and Research*, Vol. 12, No. 11, pp. 20-24.
- Ragghianti, C.L. (1974) "Dall'Arte al Museo", *Arte, fare e vedere*, Vol. 1, Firenze.
- Vital, R. et al. (2023) Comparison of extended reality platforms and tools for viewing and exhibiting art, *Digital Applications in Archaeology and Cultural Heritage*, Vol. 31, e00298, pp. 1-15.
- Webber, M. (2018) The Instrumentalization of Contemporary Art in Bosnia-Herzegovina, Phd Thesis in Philosophy in Social Anthropology (2015-18), University College of London, London.

IFKAD 2025

Organized by:

University of Naples Federico II
LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro
Arts for Business

Associated Partners:

International Association for Knowledge Mngt
Ipazia - Observatory on Gender Research
Institute of Knowledge Asset Mngt
AiIG - Assoc. Italiana di Ingegneria Gestionale
MICS - Made in Italy Circolare e Sostenibile
Apeiron Aps
National Chengchi University
Industry+Innovation LABORatories

IFKAD 2025 Book of Presented Papers Collection
ISBN: 978-88-96687-18-5